

From pilot projects to a mammoth national programme: The story of Mission 2007

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SAM PITRODA, TELECOM pioneer and chairman of India's Knowledge Commission, said: "True knowledge can empower people at all levels. It can make our people aware of their rights and responsibilities. It can also provide them tools and techniques to be productive and meaningful in the information age. To achieve this, the best brains in the country will have to focus urgently on solving problems of the poor and the underprivileged at the bottom of the pyramid."

India is home to a number of development initiatives. We will see how one of them, which uses access to knowledge as a key to holistic development, has led to perhaps the largest ever scaling up operation in the history of the telecentres movement.

ICT makes a difference to a fishing village

Veerampattinam is a fairly large village ten kilometers south of Pondicherry on the eastern coast of southern India. A clean village with rectangular roads and a wide beach, it has a population of about 6,200 people, most of who belong to fishing families. At the centre of the village is a reputed temple, a clean square-shaped water tank paved with granite stones on all sides, the village school, a few shops, the marketplace, and the office of the local Panchayat (the traditional village government).

But seven years ago the villagers requested the M S Swaminathan Research Foundation (MSSRF) to set up a knowledge centre similar to the ones it had set up in nearby villages with financial support from the International Development Research Centre in Canada. The villagers provided space for the knowledge centre in one half of a rectangular room that serves as the Veerampattinam Panchayat office. Within months of its inauguration, the knowledge centre started providing, among other information, forecasts of wave heights and wave current directions in the Bay of Bengal 48 hours in advance. These forecasts, based on information downloaded from a US Navy website, proved to be a boon. Ever since this service was started, not one person from the village has died while fishing at sea. Before then, up to half a dozen lives were lost every year when fishermen were caught in rough weather while fishing far away from the shore.

In the case of the fishermen of Veerampattinam, lives could not have been saved without the intelligent use of a combination of old and new technologies. The US Navy gathers the information on weather conditions in the Bay of Bengal through its own satellites and puts out the information on its website. MSSRF has set up, in cooperation with local communities, about a dozen knowledge centres in villages within 30 kilometers of each other, all of which are connected to a hub at a central village through a hybrid wired and wireless local area network. Each knowledge centre, managed by local volunteers trained by MSSRF, is provided with a few personal

computers with a solar powered battery backup to ensure an uninterrupted power supply, a printer, and a web camera.

One computer in each centre is connected to the server at the hub through telephone-and-modem or spread spectrum technology or a Motorola very high frequency two-way radio to enable them to receive and transmit data, text, audio and video files. The staff at the hub download wave height forecasts from the US Navy site once a day and transmit them as a multimedia file to Veerampattinam. The transferred message consists of a weather chart in colour indicating wave heights as a function of the distance from the shore and current ocean directions, a written statement and a voice announcement. At Veerampattinam a local volunteer downloads the message, puts up the weather chart and the written statement on the notice board and broadcasts the voice announcement several times in a day over the public address system so everyone in the village can hear it through strategically located loudspeakers.

All the knowledge centres, including the one at Veerampattinam, distribute the twice-monthly local language community newspaper called *Our Village News*, edited and produced by a consortium of knowledge centre volunteers and provides news on employment opportunities. A number of able-bodied village youths from Veerampattinam have been selected as firemen and a couple of them have joined the security forces. Many school kids visit the knowledge centre to learn to use computers. The centre has helped a woman's self-help group to make and market ready-to-wear clothing.

During and after the tsunami

The knowledge centre at Veerampattinam played a key role in saving lives of on the 26th of December 2004, when rumblings of the earth off the coast of Aceh in Indonesia sent the deadly tsunami waves to its shores. On the day of the tsunami, Mani, one of the Panchayat members, was on the shore mending his net when he saw something unusual — the sea receding hundreds of feet. He thought that something awful was going to happen and rushed to the knowledge centre along with a few others, broke open the door and started warning over the public address system requesting everyone in the village to vacate their homes and rush to safety.

By the time the giant waves struck the village and dragged boats from the shore half a kilometer into the village, everyone — including women, children, the old and infirm — were already in safe areas. The villagers lost some of their homes, boats, nets and other valuables, but there was hardly any loss of lives. And when the relief supplies came, knowledge centre volunteer Mr Elumalai used the public address system to request people to come street by street and collect rice, cooking oil, kerosene and other supplies. Whereas in most other tsunami-affected areas the supplies did not reach the

right people and there were chaotic scenes, the distribution of relief materials at Veerampattinam was orderly. Clearly people who are used to a culture of sharing and communicating information in their daily lives are better able to deal with disasters.

A knowledge centre managed by women

If the knowledge centre at Veerampattinam saves fishermen’s lives, the one in the agricultural village of Embalam has helped women acquire a certain level of gender equality. Like all knowledge centres set up by MSSRF, the Embalam centre was also set up after detailed negotiations with the people of the village — men and women, old and young, landed and landless. Although a variety of technologies are used, the focus of the Information Village Research Project, funded by Canada’s IDRC, is people, their contexts and their needs. As in other villages, the bottom-up programme started with a needs assessment. About a third of the population in most of these villages has an income of less than USD25 per month and there is a great need for implementing poverty reduction programmes. The Embalam knowledge centre is managed by an all-women team selected by the women self-help groups in the village. The information provided is wide ranging and pertains to agriculture, education, healthcare, animal health, government entitlements, employment opportunities, market information and livelihood opportunities.

Thanks to a training programme offered through the knowledge centre, volunteers at this centre are checking villagers eyesight for long and short sight, cataracts. They then transmit pictures taken with a web camera along with their observations as email attachments to doctors at the nearby Aravind Eye Hospital, who provide free treatment to those who need it. Some women have set up small-scale business operations, such as knitting sweaters and growing mushrooms. All the self-help groups use accounting software

specially developed for the purpose by MSSRF scientists to maintain their micro-finance programmes. This software is loaded in computers in all knowledge centres.

A holistic approach to development

The project is designed to provide knowledge on demand to meet local needs, and it does so through a bottom-up process. The process starts with volunteer teams that help poll the villagers to find out what knowledge they want. MSSRF provides the villages with hardware and maintenance for the communication system, and specially designed Web sites in the local language that convey the requested information.

After visiting some of these knowledge centres Professor Bruce Alberts, former President of the National Academy of Sciences of the US, observed: “Drawing on this concept, I envision a global electronic network that connects scientists to people at all levels — farmers’ organizations and village women, for example. The network will allow them to easily access the scientific and technical knowledge that they need to solve local problems and enhance the quality of their lives, as well as to communicate their own insights and needs back to scientists”. Note the emphasis on two-way communication.

In villages where they have established knowledge centres, a group of MSSRF scientists are helping people to learn new skills. For example, a self-help group called Rani Jhansi, consisting of women from the historically marginalized Dalit communities, is making and marketing hand-made paper and paper products. Other women, with eight years of schooling or less are making biopesticides, the production of which requires a certain degree of sophisticated skills. While the paper unit has yet to reap big profits, the biopesticide units are doing well. What is important is not just the money these women have started earning but the way it helps them to make their

children's lives better. Independent evaluation has shown that ICT-enabled knowledge centres can indeed make a difference to the lives of rural communities.

It is not enough to provide useful information. It is important to see that the people who receive the information are empowered to use it to their advantage. Poverty will persist so long as a large proportion of the rural population is engaged only in unskilled work. Knowledge centres should bring about a paradigm shift from unskilled to skilled work and from on-farm to value-added non-farm activities. For that to happen, people may need to acquire new skills and funds. Also, we should learn to use ICTs to bridge gender, social, economic and technological divides. The challenge is in adopting a holistic information access-enabled development strategy and using ICTs as a cross-cutting instrument in different aspects of the strategy.

The project is people centred and participatory, and technology is seen as an enabler. It is holistic and ensures the timely provision of information and enables people to take advantage of information through capacity building, formation of self-help groups, facilitating micro-credit and setting up micro-enterprises.

From a small beginning to a mass movement

MSSRF has embarked on extending these benefits to other regions of the world. This is primarily through two communication initiatives, the annual South-South Exchange Traveling Workshop (SSE) and the Open Knowledge Network (OKN).

So far three SSEs have been held and each had 20-25 development activists from Asia, Africa and Latin America as participants. Participants travel from village to village in Pondicherry and Tamil Nadu, where MSSRF has set up knowledge centres, and engage in a dialogue with the local people and knowledge centre volunteers.

They share their knowledge and learn from one another's experience. After a week-long journey covering about ten villages, the whole group analyze the lessons learnt and how they could use the experiential learning in their own work.

In collaboration with OneWorld International, MSSRF formed the OKN, a human network, which collects, shares and disseminates local knowledge and is supported by flexible technical solutions.

Conceived by Peter Armstrong, OKN is a fabulous idea and one day it will become the equivalent of the Internet for poor people in the world. Its aim is to empower the poor through the creation and sharing of local content. What people need is space to communicate, to express their ideas and their voices. OKN helps them acquire the skills to develop content. People in rural areas of India and Africa are partners in this network and partners from countries such as Sri Lanka and Nepal are joining in. Trained volunteers gather indigenous knowledge by talking to people and upload the information along with metadata on to a central portal. While the main content could be in any language, the metadata is in English. Anyone anywhere can download the content and using the metadata tags choose what is relevant to one's needs.

MSSRF has now launched what is perhaps the largest ever scaling up programme in the history of ICT-enabled development. This is called Mission 2007: Every Village a Knowledge Centre. The idea is to reach out to all the 637,000 villages of India by the 60th anniversary of India's Independence on August 15 2007.

Winning support

As a first step to win support, MSSRF set up the MSSRF-Jamsetji Tata National Virtual Academy for Food Security and Rural Prosperity (NVA) in August 2003, with financial support from the Tata Social

Welfare Trust. Unlike the major science academies of the world, the NVA is an academy of grassroots workers who have distinguished themselves by their commitment to public good and community welfare. The Mission of spreading the knowledge revolution cannot succeed without the support of a very large number of such committed grassroots workers spread all over the country. The idea is to select more than a million such Fellows, with at least one man and one woman from each of India's 637,000 villages.

MSSRF followed this up through a series of consultations where they invited government leaders, bureaucrats, academics, civil societies and industry. They discussed building on the experience of MSSRF and others by taking ICT-enabled knowledge provision to resource-poor families. Having won support for the formation of Mission 2007: Every Village a Knowledge Centre to facilitate the setting up of village knowledge centres throughout rural India to generate knowledge-based livelihoods, MSSRF formed a National Alliance for carrying out the Mission. Currently, there are more than 160 partners in the Alliance, which is perhaps one of the largest multi stakeholder partnerships in development. They include ministries and departments of the government, academia, NGOs, industry, research institutions, international organizations and financial institutions.

Initially, there was considerable diffidence about achieving such a huge task in less than three years. But subsequent developments on many fronts have led to greater confidence. Together with OneWorld South Asia, MSSRF organized the first convention of Mission 2007 in New Delhi in July 2004, where partner organizations agreed upon a common goal and a joint action framework. The workshop highlighted the need for policy intervention, such as de-licensing and making the highly regulatory environment more people friendly. The Mission would be implemented on the principles of social inclusion, social relevance and gender equality, and transaction costs would be kept low. An ICT-SHG movement would be fostered to give a sense of ownership to the people. The Alliance would work with Panchayats, self-help groups, common interest groups, and community-based organizations.

The Alliance would also promote entrepreneurship in the villages and address the growing concern about adverse social, economic and political implications of the expanding urban-rural divide in knowledge, skills and technological empowerment. The National Alliance would be a coalition of the concerned and would function like the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR), without a formal structure. The Alliance would have informal organizational structures at national, state, district and local levels to plan and implement the objectives of the Mission. Several task forces would be constituted to deal with connectivity, content, capacity building, coordination and management. These task forces have since submitted detailed reports that were discussed in July 2005 at the second convention of Mission 2007.

Inaugurating the convention, the President of India, Dr Abdul Kalam, said the connectivity of village complexes to provide economic opportunities to all segments of people was needed to bridge the urban-rural divide, generate employment and enhance rural prosperity. He was immensely pleased to hand over the Fellowships to the first batch of over 130 Fellows of the NVA. The Finance Minister of India, Mr Palaniappan Chidambaram, announced his readiness to allocate start-up funds to the tune of USD1.5bn to implement the programme. The Minister for IT, Mr Dayanidhi Maran announced that his ministry would join the Mission by setting up 100,000 community service centres. The Minister for Panchayat Raj, Mr Mani Shankar Iyer, offered the support of his ministry and suggested that the village knowledge

centres could be set up in Panchayat office buildings throughout the country. The union minister of state for planning, Mr Rajasekharan, suggested that banks should provide youths funds to establish village knowledge centres.

In addition to connectivity and access issues, the Mission will address content. A consortium of content providers will be formed to build a location and language-specific knowledge base. There is also a need for capacity building for content provisioning, as well as building a framework for learning-by-doing by practitioners. The Mission is also focusing on gender mainstreaming of content; assured and remunerative market-linking of producers and purchasers; outsourcing of work from towns to villages; ICT-SHGs at low transaction cost; organising financial, technical and infrastructure resources; and training and capacity building.

Mission 2007 is keen to promote community radio and Internet radio to unleash the creativity of rural people. Banks will have to play a catalytic role to introduce new schemes through rural knowledge centres. There is also a need to undertake cost-benefit analysis and to document best practice and success stories.

The time is ripe for ushering in the knowledge revolution in rural India. The Telecom Regulatory Authority is now building strategies to accelerate the growth of telecom infrastructures and to cut communication costs. Many national institutions, such as state open universities and the National Informatics Centre, are keen to reach out to the rural masses. State governments are interested in harnessing ICTs for sustainable development. ISRO has launched a satellite called Edusat that is dedicated to education as well as the knowledge centers programme. The Ministry of Health is keen to use ICT infrastructure to take healthcare to rural areas.

It is significant that the Mission talks about every village being a knowledge centre and not a knowledge centre in every village, thus recognizing the enormous indigenous knowledge native to village people.

